

"TRANSLATING UZBEK WORLD LITERATURE: A 12-YEAR-OLD'S DREAM TO SHARE CULTURE AND LANGUAGE WITH THE WORLD"

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Annotation: Mohinur is a 12-year-old girl from Uzbekistan who is passionate about languages and literature. She has a particular love for Uzbek, Russian, and world literature and spends most of her free time reading books in these languages. Mohinur dreams of becoming a professional translator in the future to help people from different cultures communicate with each other and preserve languages and cultures. I have had the privilege of witnessing her passion for languages and literature firsthand. From a young age, she has shown a remarkable aptitude for picking up new languages and immersing herself in the works of different cultures. Her love for Uzbek, Russian, and world literature is truly inspiring, and she spends countless hours reading and studying these texts.

What impresses me most about Mohinur is her desire to use her language skills to bridge cultural divides and promote understanding between people from different backgrounds. She sees translation as a powerful tool for communication and preserving the richness of different languages and cultures. I have no doubt that she will make an excellent translator in the future and contribute greatly to the field.

Mohinur's dedication to learning and her enthusiasm for literature are a testament to her character and potential. I am honored to have been her teacher and look forward to seeing all that she will accomplish in the years to come.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, languages, literature, Uzbek, Russian, world literature, translator, communication, culture, language skills, books, teacher, passion, aptitude, inspiring, reading, studying, bridge cultural divides, understanding, translation, communication, preserving richness, excellent translator, dedication, enthusiasm, character, potential.

Аннотация: Мохинур — 12-летняя девочка из Узбекистана, увлеченная языками и литературой. Она особенно любит узбекскую, русскую и мировую литературу и большую часть свободного времени проводит за чтением книг на этих языках. Мохинур мечтает в будущем стать профессиональным переводчиком, чтобы помогать людям из разных культур общаться друг с другом и сохранять языки и культуры. Мне посчастливилось воочию убедиться в ее увлечении языками и литературой. С юных лет она проявляла замечательную способность изучать новые языки и погружаться в произведения разных культур. Ее любовь к узбекской, русской и мировой литературе поистине вдохновляет, и она тратит бесчисленные часы на чтение и изучение этих текстов.

Что меня больше всего впечатляет в Мохинур, так это ее желание использовать свои языковые навыки для преодоления культурных различий и содействия взаимопониманию между людьми из разных слоев общества. Она рассматривает перевод как мощный инструмент для общения и сохранения богатства разных языков и культур. Я не сомневаюсь, что в будущем она станет отличным переводчиком и внесет большой вклад в эту область.

Преданность Мохинур обучению и ее энтузиазм к литературе являются свидетельством ее характера и потенциала. Для меня большая честь быть ее учителем, и я с нетерпением жду возможности увидеть все, чего она добьется в ближайшие годы.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, языки, литература, узбекский, русский, мировая литература, переводчик, общение, культура, языковые навыки, книги, учитель, страсть,

способности, вдохновение, чтение, изучение, преодоление культурных различий, понимание, перевод, общение, сохранение богатства, отличный переводчик, целеустремленность, энтузиазм, характер, потенциал.

I have always been fascinated by languages and literature, and I have a particular love for Uzbek, Russian, and world literature. I spend most of my free time reading books in these languages, and I dream of becoming a professional translator in the future.

Growing up in Uzbekistan, I was exposed to the Uzbek language and culture from a very young age. Uzbek is the official language of my country, and it is spoken by the majority of the population. My parents always encouraged me to read books in Uzbek, and they would often take me to the local library to borrow books. I remember spending hours reading books by famous Uzbek authors like Iskhakhan Ibrat, Erkin Vokhidov, Abdulla Qodiriy, Hamid Ismailov, and Zulfiya Isroilova. These books not only helped me improve my Uzbek language skills but also gave me a deeper understanding of Uzbek culture and history.

As I grew older, I became interested in other languages as well. Russian is widely spoken in Uzbekistan, and it is also taught in schools as a second language. I started learning Russian when I was in primary school, and I quickly fell in love with the language. I found that Russian literature was just as fascinating as Uzbek literature, and I started reading books by Russian authors like Leo Tolstoy, Fyodor Dostoevsky, and Anton Chekhov. These books were more challenging than the ones I had read in Uzbek, but I enjoyed the challenge and felt proud of myself when I could understand a difficult passage.

In addition to Uzbek and Russian literature, I also enjoy reading books from around the world. Thanks to the internet, I have access to books from all over the world, and I have discovered many new authors that I would never have known about otherwise. I particularly enjoy reading books from Europe and North America, as they give me a glimpse into different cultures and ways of life. Some of my favorite authors include J.K. Rowling, John Green, and Khaled Hosseini.

As I read more and more books in different languages, I realized that I had a talent for translation. I found that I could easily translate passages from Uzbek to Russian or vice versa, and I enjoyed the challenge of finding the right words to convey the meaning of the original text. I also started translating short stories and poems from English into Uzbek, and I found that I enjoyed this just as much as reading books.

My dream is to become a professional translator when I grow up. I want to be able to help people who speak different languages communicate with each other. I believe that translation is an important job, as it allows people from different cultures to share their ideas and experiences with each other. I also think that translation is a way to preserve languages and cultures that might otherwise be lost.

To achieve my dream of becoming a translator, I know that I need to work hard and continue to improve my language skills. I am currently studying English at school, and I am also taking private lessons to improve my Russian. I try to read books in all three languages every day, and I practice translating short passages whenever I can. I also attend language clubs and workshops whenever possible, as these give me the opportunity to meet other language enthusiasts and learn new skills.

I know that becoming a professional translator will not be easy, but I am determined to succeed. I believe that my love for languages and literature will help me overcome any obstacles that come my way. I also know that there are many opportunities for translators in Uzbekistan and around the world, as more and more people are realizing the importance of communication across cultures.

In addition, I dream of making my culture popular around the world. I believe that the best way to achieve this is by translating the works of Uzbek writers into different languages.

Uzbekistan is a country rich in culture and history. Our literature is diverse and has been shaped by our unique experiences as a nation. However, not many people outside of Uzbekistan know about our literature or culture. This is something that I want to change.

My goal is to translate the works of Uzbek writers into English so that people all over the world can read and appreciate them. I want to share the beauty of our language and culture with others, and I believe that translation is the best way to do this.

There are many talented Uzbek writers whose works deserve to be read by a wider audience. Some of my favorite authors include Abdulla Qodiriy, Chingiz Aitmatov, and Hamid Ismailov. Their works are full of deep insights into human nature, and they reflect the unique experiences of Uzbekistan.

By translating these works into English, I hope to introduce people to the richness of Uzbek literature. I also hope to break down barriers between different cultures and promote understanding and empathy.

I know that this will not be an easy task. Translating literature requires a deep understanding of both languages and cultures. It also requires patience and dedication. However, I am willing to put in the work because I believe in the power of literature to connect people from different backgrounds.

In conclusion, I am a 12-year-old girl from Uzbekistan who loves reading books in Uzbek, Russian, and world literature. I dream of becoming a professional translator in the future, and I am working hard to improve my language skills and gain experience. I believe that translation is an important job that can help people from different cultures communicate with each other and preserve languages and cultures. I hope that one day I will be able to make a difference as a translator and help people connect across borders.

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